

Recycled concrete paving block waste as a selected sustainable substitute for natural aggregate in cement composites

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ABSTRACT

This study examines the impact of replacing natural aggregates with second-quality sorted concrete paving block (CPB) aggregates in mortars and concretes. Substitution levels varied from 0 % to 100 % for fine aggregates in mortars and 50 % for fine and/or coarse aggregates in concretes. The research analysed the properties of the waste material, including particle size distribution, porosity, water absorption, and density. For mortars and concretes, the evaluated parameters encompassed workability, consistency, density, compressive strength, electrical resistivity, and microstructure. The findings indicate that mortars incorporating CPB aggregates necessitate higher dosages of superplasticizers to achieve desired workability. This requirement is attributed to the increased cement content per unit volume and the finer particle size of the recycled aggregates. Early compressive strength of mortars peaks at a 50 % recycled aggregate content due to a reduced effective water-to-cement ratio, while 100 % substitution of fine aggregate leads to a significant decrease in compressive strength. Concretes with recycled aggregates exhibit comparable or superior early compressive strength relative to reference concrete, but after 28 days, all concretes with recycled aggregates display lower strength. The 28-day compressive strengths are 65.9 MPa, 64.8 MPa, and 62.3 MPa for 50 % replacement by fine, coarse, and a combination of both aggregates, respectively. These results surpass those achieved in similar studies. Durability assessments suggest that concrete mixtures with CPB exhibit trends comparable to reference concrete, indicating moderate resistance to chloride penetration. Overall, the findings suggest that utilizing sorted CPB aggregates is a viable approach to replacing natural aggregates in mortars and concretes.

1. Introduction

Due to concrete being the most extensively used construction material globally, demand has surged over the past fifty years, driven by population growth and the growing need for residential and infrastructure projects. This increase in demand has significantly increased the demand for construction raw materials, with aggregates accounting for about 70–80 % of the total volume of concrete [1,2]. The construction industry consumed approximately 21.0, 40.0 and 48.3 billion metric tons (Mt) of aggregates worldwide in 2007, 2014 and 2015 respectively [3]. Presently, this number increases by approximately 5 % annually [4]. Given this substantial increase in aggregate consumption, the availability of natural aggregate (NA) is becoming insufficient to meet the construction industry's demands in some regions, both in terms

of quantity and quality. Growing concerns about the environmental impact of the construction industry's extensive use of raw materials, such as aggregates, have intensified; consequently, there is an urgent need to identify alternative aggregate resources [5].

Construction and demolition waste (CDW) generated globally has consistently been a significant portion of the total waste produced. Those produced during renovation and demolition, which amount to 4.5 billion tons globally presents a viable and sustainable option for concrete production. China leads in this regard, producing 2360 Mt of concrete waste annually. India follows as the second-largest contributor, generating roughly 700 Mt of CDW each year. The United States ranks third, with an annual output of 600 Mt of CDW [3,6]. On average, the European Union generates more than 800 Mt of CDW annually [7,8]. This accounts for more than 37 % of the total waste generated in the EU

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[9]. During the past 10 years, this figure has remained relatively stable, reflecting the large scale of construction and demolition activities throughout the region. A significant portion of CDW consists of excavated materials, which are widely recognized for having a minimal environmental impact during disposal [10,11]. However, the overall environmental impact remains a concern, primarily due to the large volume of CDW, which raises issues related to transportation and land use. The use of recycled aggregates from CDW in concrete production has gained significant attention in recent years due to its potential to reduce environmental impacts and promote sustainability in the construction industry [12–14]. However, the integration of these recycled materials into concrete poses challenges, particularly concerning the mechanical properties of the resulting mixtures.

Studies have highlighted that while certain enhancement methods, such as the use of supplementary cementitious materials (SCMs) and admixtures, can improve the strength and durability of concrete with recycled aggregates, issues like increased water absorption and variability in aggregate quality often lead to decreased performance [15–17]. Therefore, balancing environmental benefits with mechanical properties of concrete remains a critical area of research in the development of sustainable building materials. Concrete made with recycled aggregates tends to exhibit lower compressive strength and increased porosity compared to concrete made with natural aggregates, which is largely caused by the weaker bonding between the recycled aggregates and the cement matrix, as well as the presence of residual mortar on the recycled aggregates, which can lead to increased water absorption and lower density [18]. Tensile strength and modulus of elasticity are often reduced when recycled aggregates are used as well [19]. These reductions can be mitigated through the use of SCMs such as fly ash, ground granulated blast-furnace slag, and silica fume, which can enhance the overall strength and durability of the concrete [20]. However, even with these enhancements, the variability in the quality of recycled aggregates, due to different sources and processing methods, remains a significant challenge. This variability can lead to inconsistent performance in the resulting concrete, making it crucial to carefully select and process recycled aggregates to achieve the desired mechanical properties while maintaining environmental benefits. This problem could be solved by sorting aggregates from recycled waste by waste type, which could help to address the issue of variability in the quality of recycled aggregates. Studies [21,22] have shown that the sorting process can improve the mechanical properties of concrete made from recycled aggregates by reducing heterogeneity and improving the consistency of the material [23]. The separation of CDW plays a significant role in improving the quality and mechanical properties of recycled aggregates used in concrete. By separating CDW into specific categories, such as concrete, bricks, tiles, and other materials, the resulting recycled aggregates can achieve more consistent and desirable properties [24,25]. This approach not only enhances the mechanical properties of recycled concrete but also aligns with sustainability goals by reducing the demand for natural aggregates and reducing the carbon footprint associated with concrete production [22].

Therefore, the research described in this paper focusses on the use of selected waste material, which are second-quality concrete paving blocks, as a partial replacement for natural aggregates in mortars and concretes and on the resulting mechanical properties of the proposed mixtures. Recent research on the use of separated crushed paving blocks as a replacement for natural aggregates in concrete has yielded diverse results. The study from 2016 [26] examined the impact of substituting natural coarse aggregates with crushed paving blocks sourced from various origins, including waste concrete pavements, factory rejects, expired pavements, and surplus construction material, at replacement levels of 50 % and 100 %, with varying water-cement (w/c) ratios. Crushed paving blocks had an absorption rate of 5.36 %, which affected both workability and strength, while natural aggregate showed an absorption rate of 1.83 % on average. This study found that increasing the substitution level significantly affected the concrete's properties; the

findings indicated that a 50 % replacement led to higher slump values but lower compressive strength, whereas a 100 % replacement achieved the highest compressive strength. Higher w/c ratios were associated with reduced compressive strength, while lower w/c ratios improved it. The study from 2020 [27] tested various replacement rates (from 10 % to 100 %) and w/c ratios to determine their impact on concrete density, compressive and flexural strengths. It has been found that increasing the replacement rate of recycled aggregates generally decreased the strength of the concrete, particularly as the w/c ratio increased. The optimal sand ratio decreased with higher replacement rates, and the addition of fly ash improved the strength over time. In 2021, research [28] focused on the use of old paving stones as both coarse and fine aggregates replacement (50 and 100 % replacement of NA) revealed that properties of old paving stones can vary depending on the age, degree of wear and typical use conditions. High absorption and low wear resistance were common characteristics. The flexural and compressive strengths were tested and showed a decrease of the results with the addition of recycled aggregate. Despite these drawbacks, specific mixtures were developed to produce new pavement blocks using recycled old paving blocks. Another study published in November 2021 [29] demonstrated that crushed concrete paving blocks can effectively replace coarse aggregates in concrete mixtures. This substitution led to several benefits, including increased compressive strength and reduced thermal conductivity. The use of crushed paving blocks was found to contribute to significant environmental improvements, such as lower levels of aquatic eutrophication and reduced mineral extraction. These findings underscore the value of utilising crushed paving blocks as a sustainable alternative to natural aggregates, offering substantial advantages in the environmental and performance assessment of building materials. The study from 2022 [30] investigated the use of paving blocks made from bricks, concrete, and granite as replacements for fine aggregates in new concrete blocks. The results revealed that granite paving blocks exhibited superior mechanical properties compared to those made from concrete and clay bricks.

2. Aim and scope

The primary objective of this research is to evaluate the properties of mortars and concretes incorporating aesthetically unsatisfactory concrete paving blocks (CPB), which were tested and subsequently crushed and used as partial and full replacements for natural aggregate. The study investigates the feasibility of utilising CPB recycled aggregates at various substitution levels; 0 %, 25 %, 50 %, 75 % and 100 % of fine aggregate in the case of mortars, and 50 % of fine aggregate, 50 % of coarse aggregate, and 50 % of fine and coarse aggregate in the case of concretes; to study their impact on both the physical and mechanical properties of fresh and hardened mortars and concretes. The scope of the research encompasses a thorough analysis of the characteristics of the recycled aggregates, including the compressive strength of the original blocks, particle size distributions, porosity, water absorption, and density. For mortars, the study examines the consistency, rheological parameters, and density of the fresh mix, along with porosity, water absorption, and compressive strength of the hardened material. In the case of concrete, the research focusses on the consistency of the fresh mix, as well as the density, porosity, water absorption, compressive strength, resistivity, and microstructure of hardened concrete. This study aims to advance sustainable construction practices by identifying optimal substitution levels that can either maintain or improve the performance of mortars and concrete while reducing the dependency on natural aggregates.

3. Novelty of the research

The novelty of this research lies in its focus on using sorted crushed concrete paving blocks as recycled aggregates for the production of mortars and concretes. Unlike mixed CDW, which can be heterogeneous

and challenging to separate, paving blocks represent a selected and relatively uniform waste material that is easier to separate from other fractions of waste. This specificity allows for a more controlled and precise analysis of the effects of recycled aggregates on the properties of mortars and concrete. By evaluating the substitution of natural aggregates with these selected recycled materials at various levels, this research aims to provide deeper insights into optimising the performance of sustainable concrete mixtures. The focus on a single, well-defined waste stream improves the relevance and applicability of the findings to real-world construction practices, where the selective recycling of particular materials can lead to more predictable and desirable outcomes in the final concrete products.

4. Used materials

4.1. Natural and recycled aggregates

The concrete paving blocks used in this study were sourced as production waste from a local Polish manufacturer. Despite being of full quality in terms of strength and durability, these blocks were selected for recycling because of aesthetic imperfections that made them unsuitable for primary commercial use. CPB were not subjected to any colouring or dyeing processes, maintaining their natural appearance (see Fig. 1). Key material properties, including compressive strength, density, porosity, and absorbability, were evaluated on three randomly selected specimens to characterise the recycled CPB's performance.

The compressive strength of CPB was tested according to EN 12390-3 [31] on three specimens with dimensions of 73x73x71 mm. Volume density, real density, and porosity were tested using methods described in EN 12390-7 [32] on three specimens with dimensions of 73x73x71 mm and the absorbability was tested according to EN 13755 [33] on the same samples. The detailed results of these tests are summarised in Table 1. The average compressive strength of the CPB was measured as 45.37 MPa, porosity and absorbability were measured as 7.91 % and 4.58 %. The average volume density was determined as 2.274 g/cm³ and the average real density was determined as 2.470 g/cm³.

Natural aggregates (NA) – natural sand with grading of 0–2 mm as a natural fine aggregate (NFA) and natural gravel with grading 2–16 mm as a natural coarse aggregate (NCA), were used to prepare the cement composites. The loose bulk density was measured as 1.660 g/cm³ and 1.680 g/cm³ for NFA and NCA respectively. The grading curves of both NA are presented in Fig. 3. Both used NAs are depicted in Fig. 4a) and b).

The CPB were crushed and ground to obtain recycled aggregate. The crushing was carried out by a jaw crusher and expected result was to reach fractions of 0–16 mm. The process is illustrated in Fig. 2.

At first paving blocks were put into jaw crusher and crushed. The particle size obtained was 0–64 mm. After crushing the material was sieved to separate fine (0–2 mm), coarse (2–16 mm) and oversize aggregate (>16 mm). The oversize aggregate was crushed once more to

Fig. 1. Non-compliant concrete paving block.

Table 1

Properties of randomly selected concrete paving block specimens.

	Compressive strength	Volume density	Real density	Porosity	Absorbability
	(MPa)	(g/cm ³)	(g/cm ³)	(%)	(%)
Sample 1	42.02	2.275	2.470	7.89	4.69
Sample 2	46.18	2.270	2.471	8.14	4.17
Sample 3	47.91	2.278	2.468	7.71	4.88
Average	45.37	2.274	2.470	7.91	4.58

Fig. 2. Scheme of recycled aggregate production.

obtain two former fractions. Based on this processing two separate fractions were obtained – fine paving block aggregate (FPBA, see Fig. 4d) and coarse paving block aggregate (CPBA, see Fig. 4c). Then the obtained material was sieved and tested to prepare grading curves. Sieve analyses were conducted according to EN 933-1 [31] on 10915.1 g of CPBA, 2758.9 g of FPBA, 6003.9 g of NCA and 3000 g of NFA. Grading curves are presented in Fig. 3. Loose bulk density was measured as 1.580 g/cm³ and 1.610 g/cm³ for FPBA and CPBA respectively.

Aggregate samples from the CPB were studied under a scanning electron microscope (SEM) equipped with an energy dispersive spectroscopy (EDS) analyser. Fig. 5 presents images of the sand particles and the presence of a circular pore in the recycled aggregate.

4.2. Aggregate mixes for mortar production

NFA and FPBA were mixed together in the manufacture process of the mortar mixes. The FPBA substitution percentages were set at 0 %, 25 %, 50 %, 75 %, and 100 %. The loose bulk density was recorded as 1.660 g/cm³, 1.640 g/cm³, 1.620 g/cm³, 1.600 g/cm³, and 1.580 g/cm³, respectively. The resulting grading curves are presented in Fig. 5.

4.3. Aggregate mixes for concrete production

The composition of aggregates for concrete preparation was as follows: for a reference mixture 100 % of natural aggregates was used, in the second mix 50 % of NFA was substituted with FPBA, in the third mix 50 % of NCA was substituted with CPBA, and in the last one the substitution of NA by 50 % of FPBA and 50 % of CPBA were used. The loose bulk density was recorded as 1.680 g/cm³, 1.670 g/cm³, 1.670 g/cm³ and 1.650 g/cm³, respectively. The resulting grading curves are

Fig. 3. Grading curves of natural and recycled aggregates.

Fig. 4. Photos of natural and recycled aggregates, a) NFA, b) NCA, c) CPBA, d) FPBA.

Fig. 5. SEM image of a recycled aggregate sample a) sand particles, b) circular pore presence.

presented in Fig. 7.

4.4. Cement, water and admixtures for the mortars and concretes production

CEM I 42.5 R Portland cement was utilised in the preparation of all mortar and concrete mixtures, with its phase composition detailed in Table 2. Ordinary tap water served as mixing water throughout the study. To achieve and maintain the target workability and consistency of the mixtures, a polycarboxylate-based superplasticizer (SP) was incorporated according to the specified mix proportions.

4.5. Mortar and concrete compositions

The compositions of the designed mortar mixes are detailed in Table 3. The amount of SP is given in grams and percentage by mass of the cement (%m.c.). Five types of mortars were developed with varying

levels of NFA by FPBA at 0 %, 25 %, 50 %, 75 %, and 100 %. The mix designations of mortars follow the format "MXX," where "XX" represents the percentage of material substitution utilised in the mix. The w/c ratio was maintained at 0.5 for all mortar mixtures.

For the rheometric test, due to the limitations of the rheometer, the original mortars were too stiff for accurate testing. To address this, the water-to-cement (w/c) ratio was increased from 0.5 to 0.55 exclusively for rheological evaluations, see Table 4. The amount of SP was adjusted in each mortar to ensure that the flow diameter matched that of the reference mortar (M0). This adjustment ensured consistency in flow behaviour, compensating for the modified w/c ratio. These modifications enabled reliable torque and rheological parameter measurements while maintaining comparable conditions across all mortar samples. In case of mortars with content of FPBA, high amount of water and superplasticizer needed to obtain consistency which could allow for testing caused segregation during testing procedure. Due to that, only M25-R and reference sample M0-R were tested, as testing other mortars

Fig. 6. Grading curves of natural and recycled aggregate mixes for mortars production.

Fig. 7. Grading curves of natural and recycled aggregate mixes for concrete production.

Table 2
Phase composition of Portland cement.

C ₃ S Alite	C ₂ S Belite	C ₃ A Celite	C ₄ AF Brown Millerite
71.1	5.6	3.9	12.7

Table 3
Mortars composition.

	CEM I 42,5 R	Water	w/ c	NFA	FPBA	SP		
	(g)	(g)	(-)	(g)	(g)	(%)	(g)	(%m. c.)
M0	450	225	0.5	1350	-	-	1	0.22
M25	450	225	0.5	1013	337	25	4.2	0.93
M50	450	225	0.5	675	675	50	7	1.56
M75	450	225	0.5	337	1013	75	12	2.67
M100	450	225	0.5	-	1350	100	16.5	3.67

would require too significant changes to basic mortar formula.

The compositions of the designed concrete mixes are detailed in Table 5. Four types of concretes were developed with varying levels of NA replaced by FPBA or CPBA. The mix designations of concretes are as follows: C-0 – reference mixture, C-50f – 50 % of NFA replacement by FPBA, C-50c – 50 % of NCA replacement by CPBA, C-50fc – 50 % of NFA and 50 % of NCA replacement by FPBA and CPBA. The w/c ratio was maintained at 0.42 for all concrete mixtures.

Table 4
Modified mortar compositions for rheological testing.

	CEM I 42,5 R	Water	w/c	Natural sand	Recycled aggregate	SP		
	(g)	(g)	(-)	(g)	(g)	(%)	(g)	(%m. c.)
M0-R	450	247.5	0.55	1350	-	-	1	0.22
M25-R	450	247.5	0.55	1013	337	25	6.2	1.38

5. Used methods

Recycled aggregates were prepared by crushing and grinding and subsequently sorted into fine and coarse grains as described in Section 4.1 of this article.

For mortars preparation and testing following standard procedures were applied:

Mortars were prepared according to EN 196-1 [34] standard.

Consistency by the flow table method based on EN 1015-3 [35] and by the penetrometer method based on EN 1015-4 [36] were tested.

The density of fresh mortar was tested according to EN 1015-6 [37].

The measurement of the rheological parameters of fresh mortar was conducted using rheometer Viskomat NT (Schleibinger Geräte), 5 and 60 min after mixing water, cement and aggregate together. The test involved measuring the torque exerted on a probe immersed in fresh mortar placed within a rotating cylinder. The rotational speed of the cylinder was programmed to increase linearly from 0 to 120 rpm during

Table 5
Concretes composition.

	CEM I 42,5 R	Water	w/c	NFA	FPBA	NCA	CPBA	SP		
	(kg)	(kg)	(-)	(kg)	(kg)	(%)	(kg)	(kg)	(%)	(kg)
C-0	9.24	3.88	0.42	10.88	-	-	32.64	-	-	14
C-50f	9.24	3.88	0.42	5.44	5.44	50	32.64	-	-	28
C-50c	9.24	3.88	0.42	10.88	-	-	16.32	16.32	50	26
C-50fc	9.24	3.88	0.42	5.44	5.44	50	16.32	16.32	50	32

the first 13 seconds. This speed was then kept constant at 120 rpm for 3 minutes, followed by a gradual linear decrease back to 0 rpm for the next 1.2 minutes. The torque measurements recorded at varying rotational speeds were analysed using a simplified Bingham model to determine the rheological parameters of the mortar:

$$M = g + hN \quad (1)$$

where M is the torque, N is the rotational speed of the measuring cylinder, g is the shear resistance, and h is the plastic flow resistance. The shear resistance g corresponds to the yield stress τ_0 while the plastic flow resistance h corresponds to the plastic viscosity η_{pl} . After the initial measurement, the fresh mortar was left to rest for one hour. Once the resting period elapsed, the mortar was manually remixed and placed back into the rotating cylinder for a second round of testing. The properties of hardened mortars were tested using European standards for each type of mixture:

The volume density of the hardened mortar was tested using the EN 1015-10 [38] standard on three beams with dimensions of 40x40x160 mm.

The real density was established using the Le Chatelier bottle method and the porosity analysis was conducted using the method described in the standard EN 1936 [39] on three specimens.

Absorbability was tested according to EN 13755 [33] on three specimens.

The mortars' compressive strength was tested according to EN 196-1 [34] standard on six specimens obtained from three beams with dimensions of 40x40x160 mm. The samples were cured for 24 hours at relative humidity (RH) equal to 95 % and temperature of 20°C in moulds and then removed and submerged in water of 20°C until the date of testing.

For concrete preparation and testing following standard procedures were applied:

Concrete mixes were prepared according to EN 206 [40], EN 12390-1 [41], and EN 12390-2 [42] standards.

The slump test for consistency was conducted according to EN 12350-2 [43].

Volume density of hardened concrete was tested using EN 12390-7 [32] standard on three cubes with dimensions of 100x100x100 mm.

The real density was established using Le Chatelier bottle method and the porosity analysis was performed using the methodology described in EN 1936 [39] on three specimens.

Absorbability was tested according to EN 13755 [33] on three specimens.

The concrete compressive strength test was carried out using EN 12390-3 [31] on three cubes with dimensions of 100x100x100 mm. The samples were cured for 24 hours at RH= 95 % and temperature of 20°C in moulds and then demoulded and submerged in water of 20°C until date of testing.

The volume (bulk) electrical resistivity of concrete mixtures was measured according to ASTM C1876 [44] using RCON tool (Giatec Scientific Inc., Canada), a non-destructive testing tool designed for this purpose, on three saturated cylindrical specimens with a diameter of 100 mm and a length of 200 mm for each concrete mixture. The specimens were placed in lime water for curing and during the whole testing period. Measurements were taken at six time points (7, 14, 28, 56, 112, and 224 days after casting) to monitor the maturation of the concrete.

From the values of the bulk electrical resistivity, the diffusion coefficients of concrete might be also determined [45].

Scanning Electron Microscope JEOL JSM-7610F Plus (JEOL, Japan) was used to observe the microstructure of the recycled aggregate and then the resulting composites. Before the analysis, the concrete samples were sputtered with approximately 20 nm thick gold (Au) layer using a turbomolecular pumped combined sputter coater and carbon evaporation system Q150V ES Plus (Quorum Technologies, England). Testing of the cross sections of the samples was performed using a backscattered electron (BSE) detector. This electron microscope is equipped with an energy-dispersive spectrometer (EDX, Oxford Instruments), which is capable of providing the chemical composition of the samples.

6. Results

6.1. Properties of fresh mortars

The results of a consistency test using the flow table method are depicted in Fig. 8 and the results of a penetration depth test using a penetrometer in Fig. 9. In the first case, a mortar flow diameter of 17.5 +/- 1 cm was aimed for. Similar mortar consistency was obtained by applying different amounts of superplasticizer. Fig. 8 clearly shows that the amount of superplasticizer required to achieve the same consistency of mortars increased with increasing FPBA content. This is an approximately linear relationship (see Fig. 8, $R^2=0.9866$). This indicates that the recycled aggregate must be properly treated prior to application to reduce its negative impact on the workability of the mix. For the latter measurement with the penetrometer, the amount of superplasticizer used to achieve the same mortar flow diameter was maintained. The visible relationship in Fig. 9 is that the penetration of the measuring device gradually decreased, even though the flow remained the same. This indicates changes in two rheological parameters of these mortars - yield stress and plastic viscosity. For this reason, measurements were also made using a rheometer, which are presented and analysed in the next paragraph.

The results of rheological test are shown in Figure 10. The test could be performed only for two samples - one without the FPBA, and for the lowest replacement rate of sand (M25), as even with high SP dosage increase, other mortars did not reach the consistency that would allow to perform the measurement without segregation. This further confirms, that adding FPBA as a sand replacement significantly affects the consistency. As it can be noticed, the yield stress of the fresh mortar was 2 times higher than that of mortar with 25 % addition of FPBA, even though the consistency of both mortars was set to be comparable when measured by flow table after 5 min (Fig. 11). After 60 min from adding water to cement, the flow diameter was still comparable for both mortars, while yield stress is still two times higher. The workability loss shapes similarly for reference mortar and mortar with 25 % addition of FPBA, as yield stress in both cases increased significantly by more than 60 %.

The plastic viscosity of the mortars (Figure 10) was higher for the mortar with FPBA addition than for the reference sample. This can be the effect of significantly higher SP addition, which can affect the viscosity of the mortar. It is also interesting that plastic viscosity did not change significantly after 60 minutes of rest, while a significant increase in yield stress was observed. The higher plastic viscosity corresponds

Fig. 8. Consistency of mortars as a function of the superplasticizer amount at steady flow diameter.

Fig. 9. Consistency of mortars as a function of the superplasticizer amount and penetration depth.

Fig. 10. Rheological parameters of fresh mortars: a) yield stress and b) plastic viscosity.

well to the results of penetrometer depth measurement (Fig. 11), which for both base mortars and mortars modified for rheological testing, has shown sharp decrease with the increase in FPBA addition. This may indicate that the test of penetrometer depth is dependent more on the plastic viscosity of the fresh mortar than the yield stress, which was previously noted in [46]. While penetrometer tests are not used in concrete technology for the measurement of viscosity, they are used as

such for other viscous fluids, such as bitumen [47].

The density of fresh mortars decreases with increasing replacement level of natural aggregate. Results are presented in Fig. 12. The FPBA is a more porous and lighter aggregate in comparison to NFA. The decrease is 2.5 % up to 7.5 % for 50 % and 100 % of sand replacement by FPBA respectively. The results correspond to the density of the hardened mortars presented in the next section.

Fig. 11. Consistency of mortars used for rheology testing as a function of the SP amount and a) flow diameter, b) penetration depth.

Fig. 12. Density of mortars in plastic state.

6.2. Properties of hardened mortars

The volume and real densities were tested for all samples of mortars. The results are presented in Fig. 13. Real density was tested using a Le Chatelier bottle. The results indicate that the real density is independent on the composition of cement composites. It is connected to the comparable composition of the paving blocks and the cement mortar itself, and directly to real density of the paving blocks as well. Volume density is related to porosity of the samples. It decreases with increasing amount

of FPBA, which is more porous than natural aggregate [48,49]. The differences are slight between adjacent results, but a difference between reference sample and the one containing 50 % and 100 % of FPBA are 5.5 % and 9.5 %, respectively. It corresponds to the porosity results presented in Fig. 14. The porosity rises from 18.1 % for the reference mixture up to 25.0 % for sample with full replacement of NA with FPBA. Together with porosity, the absorptivity increases as well. This is shown in Fig. 15. It reaches 12.6 % for 100 % FPBA containing sample and is compared to 9.0 % for reference one. The problem of increased

Fig. 14. Porosity and absorptivity of mortars.

Fig. 13. Density of hardened mortars.

Fig. 15. Average values and standard deviations of compressive strength of mortars.

porosity and absorbability of mortars is related to their durability, because aggressive agents may enter the microstructure of cement composite more easily [50].

The compressive strength of the mortars was tested after 3, 7, 28 and 112 days of curing. Two different patterns may be observed. The first one is true for the early strength tested after 3 and 7 days. The compressive strength is increasing together with the replacement level, reaching its optimum at 50 % of FPBA. Over this amount, the compressive strength drops. After 3 days, the compressive strength of the sample containing 50 % of FPBA is 12 % higher than that of the reference mixture. The full replacement decreased the strength by 21 %. After 7 days, the maximum strength is 19 % better than for the reference sample, and the decrease for full replacement is only 6 %. The improvement of compressive strength at early times is connected to a greater absorbability of recycled aggregate, which caused a decrease in the effective water-cement ratio [51]. The decrease of strength after replacing more than 50 % of NA with FPBA is related to a lower compressive strength of the recycled aggregate in comparison to the natural one. This difference is overridden by the lowered w/c ratio mentioned before only up to a specific replacement level.

The second pattern is visible in the case of normal and late compressive strengths; see Fig. 15, which provides average values and standard deviations. The compressive strength after 112 days is very similar for all samples containing 0–75 % of FPBA. The difference is observed for the one containing 100 % substitution, for which the compressive strength is significantly lower. This is caused due to the fact that the cement matrix gained its final mechanical parameters, which are better than those of recycled aggregate. The role of the aggregate in the shaping of the compressive strength is proportionally lower. The compressive strength after 28 days exhibits elements from both patterns. The enhancement is visible up to the replacement level of 50 %, but it is only an improvement by 6 %. Samples containing 25 % and 75 % of FPBA are of the same compressive strength as a reference sample. A significant drop in strength can also be observed with a 100 % replacement level (12.6 % on average compared to the reference concrete). The distressing fact is a slight decrease in strength between 28th and 112th day for the samples with 50 % of FPBA. This drop is within the standard deviation range for both sample series, but it may require further long-term research.

The percentage increase in compressive strength between test dates is shown in Fig. 15. Between 3rd and 7th day the lowest relative increase is evident for reference mortar (11 %). The increase is greater for mortars with more recycled aggregate, reaching 21 % for 100 % replacement level. This behaviour is strictly related to effective water-cement ratio decreasing proportionally to recycled aggregate content. Between 7th and 28th day the greatest increase is visible for the reference mortar (29 %) and all other increases are similar (20 ± 3 %). This is a proof of previously suggested explanation of the fact that the strength of natural aggregate is taking over the effect of effective w/c ratio. The opposite

behaviour is exhibited between 28th and 112th day, for which the relative increase is the greatest for the highest replacement level. This behaviour suggests that for 0 %–75 % recycled aggregate content the final compressive strength of mortar is achieved. The last one, with 100 % of recycled aggregate may still gain some more strength after 112th day.

6.3. Properties of fresh concretes

After examining the mortars, larger-scale tests were carried out in the case of concrete mixtures to confirm the results obtained. Four concrete mixes were prepared, the reference one, one with 50 % of fine aggregate substitution, one with 50 % of coarse aggregate substitution, and the last one with 50 % replacement of both aggregates. The consistency of concrete is presented in Fig. 17. It was aimed to reach S2 slump class according to EN 12350–2 [43]. Concrete mix with 50 % of FPBA required double the dosage of superplasticizer to obtain the same slump height. A similar amount of superplasticizer was required for the mix with 50 % replacement of coarse aggregate and the one with 50 % replacement of both aggregates, but the slump was 2–3 cm higher. In general, any substitution of natural aggregate by recycled one cause greater superplasticizer consumption. Surprisingly, a similar amount of superplasticizer resulted in slightly better consistency for concretes with fine and coarse recycled aggregate together in comparison to concrete containing substitution of 50 % of fine aggregate only. This behaviour and its slight difference compared to mortars consistency is caused by a lower w/c ratio and very different proportions of cement and aggregate in concrete and mortar.

6.4. Properties of hardened concretes

The density of concrete corresponds to the density of mortars. Results are presented in Fig. 18. The real density is almost the same, although there is a bigger difference between reference concrete and those containing recycled aggregate than in the case of mortars, for which it was almost invisible. The drop in volume density is between 3.5 % and 5.5 % and is more significant than the real density. Every level of substitution resulted in a decrease of bulk density. As in the case of mortars, this is due to the higher porosity of the recycled aggregate. Those results are consistent with porosity and absorbability as presented in Fig. 19. The porosity of concrete increases from 12.1 % up to 14.4–15.0 % and the absorbability increases from 4.7 % up to 5.8 %–6.8 % depending on the type of aggregate replaced.

The compressive strength results for concretes are presented in Fig. 20 in a form of average values and standard deviations. In this case, it is more difficult to find similar patterns that are clear for mortars, but some are visible. In the case of testing 3 days after casting, the replacement of natural aggregate with recycled one resulted in an increase of compressive strength. It is connected to a lower effective water-

Fig. 16. Relative change of compressive strength of mortars between different testing dates.

Fig. 17. Consistency (slump test) of concretes and superplasticizer amount.

Fig. 18. Density of concretes.

Fig. 19. Porosity and absorbability of concretes.

cement ratio caused by the greater absorbability of this aggregate. Compressive strength of concrete with 50 % of FPBA substitution is greater than of the one with 50 % of CPBA. This is caused by even greater absorption of water by finer aggregate. Replacement of 50 % of both aggregates resulted in the best compressive strength. The maximum increase is 20.8 % and 8.2 % after 3 and 7 days respectively. After 28 and 112 days the compressive strength is lower for every concrete with recycled aggregate. The lowest value is for both aggregates replaced by 50 %. This is a perfect confirmation of the same behaviour (second pattern) of the compressive strength of mortars. The maximum drop of compressive strength is 10.5 and 16.5 % after 28 and 112 days, respectively.

Percentage expressing increase of compressive strength of concrete between each term of testing is presented in Fig. 21. Between 3rd and 7th day the relative increase of the reference concrete and those containing 50 % of fine or coarse recycled aggregate is similar and close to 30 %. Replacement of 50 % of both aggregates leads to smaller increase of 24 %. This is a slightly different behaviour compared to mortars, but it should be remembered that the scale effect of these materials is also different, and the overall aggregate content is much higher in concrete. In the case of mortars, the aggregate/cement ratio is 3 and for concrete it is almost 5. The second distinguishing factor is the presence of coarse aggregate. The relative increase between 7th and 28th day of testing shows lower values. The results indicate that replacement of coarse aggregate leads to higher relative increase than replacement of finer one only. Similarly to previous comparison replacement of both aggregates leads to the smallest increase. Between 28th and 112th day only the reference concrete changed its strength significantly. It suggests that concrete with recycled aggregate achieved the final strength.

The average values and standard deviations of bulk electrical resistivity of the concrete specimens was measured over six time points (7, 14, 28, 56, 112, and 224 days) to monitor the aging of concrete, see Fig. 22. Initial measurements at 7 days showed that samples C-50fc (5.07 kΩcm), C-50f (5.32 kΩcm), and C-50c (5.00 kΩcm) were close to the reference value of 5.22 kΩcm, indicating comparable early hydration progress. By day 28, all samples reached similar resistivity values to the reference (6.73 kΩcm), with minimal variation across samples (C-50f: 6.73, C-50f: 6.87, C-50c: 6.50 kΩcm). As the concrete matured, the differences in resistivity narrowed further. By day 112, the samples closely matched the reference resistivity (8.73 kΩcm), with C-50fc (8.42 kΩcm), C-50f (8.50 kΩcm), and C-50c (8.22 kΩcm). At the final measurement point (224 days), the resistivity of C-50f (9.47 kΩcm) and C-50c (9.50 kΩcm) converged with the reference (9.50 kΩcm), while C-50fc (8.98 kΩcm) remained slightly lower. These results demonstrate that all concrete mixtures exhibited consistent resistivity trends over time, with minor deviations that did not significantly affect overall performance compared to the reference concrete. All concrete mixtures can be classified as having moderate resistance to chloride penetration according to [52], because the results are in the range of 5.2–10.4 kΩcm.

Fig. 20. Average values and standard deviations of compressive strength of concretes.

Fig. 21. Relative change of compressive strength of concrete between different testing dates.

Fig. 22. Average values and standard deviations of bulk electrical resistivity of concretes.

6.5. Microstructure of the concrete

At first, the microstructure of the recycled aggregate was observed under SEM equipped with EDS analyser. Fig. 23 shows a sand particle in the recycled aggregate. It consists of silicone oxide and is slightly covered with calcium compounds coupled with traces of aluminium and magnesium. Fig. 24 presents the average area of recycled aggregate. The EDS analysis indicates the presence of silicone, calcium, aluminium, magnesium, sodium, and potassium compounds. Sulphur and iron are visible as well. The Fig. 25 presents an average area of “new” cement matrix in the reference mortar. Fig. 26b presents recycled aggregate (consisting of “old” cement matrix and “old” sand) embedded in “new” cement matrix. It was distinguished using the EDS analyser that there is clearly a visible similarity of the EDS spectrum presented in Fig. 24e)

and Fig. 26e). There are similar proportions of silicone and calcium – the peaks are almost the same. The similarity between EDS spectrum in Fig. 25 g) and Fig. 26 g) is visible as significantly smaller peak of silicone in comparison to calcium.

7. Discussion

The results of the present research showed a reduction in the consistency of both mortars and concretes. This is reflected in the increasing need for superplasticizers with increasing levels of replacement of natural aggregates with recycled aggregates. This phenomenon is related to the porosity and absorbability of cement composites, which were also within the scope of this research, and it has also been confirmed in previous research [53–55]. The presence of old mortar, which is less

Fig. 23. SEM image of the sand particle in recycled aggregate. a) SEM image (25µm), b) EDS element map (25µm), c) silicon map (50µm), d) calcium map (50µm), e) EDS spectrum of whole area.

Fig. 24. Average SEM image of the sand particle surrounded by cement matrix of recycled aggregate. a) SEM image (25µm), b) EDS element map (25µm), c) silicon map (25µm), d) calcium map (25µm), e) EDS spectrum of whole area.

dense and more porous than natural aggregates, contributes to greater demand for water during mixing process, which can result in inconsistent water-cement ratios, adversely affecting the workability and consistency of the mortar [56–58]. The rough texture of recycled concrete aggregate (RCA), attributed to the presence of old mortar, further exacerbates this problem, as it increases friction between particles, making

the mixture less workable. As a result, achieving the desired consistency often requires the addition of superplasticizers or other admixtures to enhance flowability and reduce water demand [59,60]. Aggregates processed by different crushing techniques may yield varying levels of adhered mortar, which affects the water absorption and the workability of the resulting concrete [61]. A second way to overcome this issue

Fig. 25. Average SEM image of cement matrix in reference sample. a) SEM image (25µm), b) EDS element map (25µm), c) silicon map (25µm), d) calcium map (25µm), e) EDS spectrum of cement matrix (whole area).

Fig. 26. SEM image of recycled aggregate embedded in new cement matrix. a) SEM image (250µm), b) EDS element map (250µm), c) silicon map (250µm), d) calcium map (250µm), e) EDS spectrum of “old” cement matrix of recycled aggregate (point 1), f) EDS spectrum of sand in recycled aggregate (point 2), g) EDS spectrum of “new” cement matrix (point 3).

might be the pre-saturation of RCA, which enhances the consistency of recycled concrete, as evidenced by increased slump values correlating with longer soaking intervals. Using saturated RCA leads to improved workability due to increased availability of free water in the concrete mixture [62].

The compressive strength of mortars and concrete was tested during the research, in the case of mortars there was a visible increase of this parameter until the substitution level of 50 %. The higher amount of recycled aggregate resulted in a decrease of strength up to 28 days of curing. After longer time, the strength of samples containing 0–75 % of

FPBA showed similar values of compressive strength. In the case of concretes, the early strength was similar or even greater as of the reference concrete, depending on the replacement level and the grading of the substituted aggregate. After 28 days and later, all concretes with recycled aggregates exhibited decreasing strength. Both phenomena have been confirmed in the literature for general CDW wastes [63].

There is not a lot of research studies focused on using sorted CPB as a replacement of NA in concrete. To the authors current knowledge, four research teams [26–29] focused on this topic during the years 2016–2021 and the results of those studies were already generally described in the introduction section. To compare the results of this study to another similar studies, w/c ratio and compressive strength at 28 days were selected, since these values were measured in all those studies. The similar mixtures (selected based on the amount of substituted NA) are given in Table 6, where the compressive strength of the used CPB is given as $f_{c,CPB}$ (in some studies, this value was not available – n.a.), the designation of the mixture used in the specific study, percentage substitution of natural fine and/or coarse aggregate, w/c ratio and concrete compressive strength at 28 days as $f_{c,28}$. However, there is a lot of other variable parameters that influence the concrete compressive strength, such as the quality of used materials (both raw and waste), use of admixtures, cement properties, used mixing processes, compaction of concrete, curing conditions, temperature and humidity and others. Based on the results, it seem that our design and used procedures led to better results of compressive strength. It needs to be also noted, that in our research the highest value of compressive strength of reference mixture was obtained in comparison to the results of compressive strength from the other considered studies. From the table, it can be also seen, that even with a lower value of compressive strength of the concrete paving block, with a good mixture design we can achieve better results of mixtures' compressive strength at similar w/c ratio. However, it is interesting that the compressive strength of the reference concrete in study by Kočí et al. [29] is such a low value. The authors explain this behaviour by the shape and sharp edges of used recycled coarse aggregate, which results in lower compressibility in comparison to used NA with round edges. Another reason for this behaviour discussed in the study [29] is that recycled aggregate have a higher bonding potential than NA because of rough surface, unfortunately, the SEM images were not provided.

For a better visual comparison, four graphs were created (see Fig. 27 - Fig. 30) that summarize the results of mixtures designed in our research and in the aforementioned studies with the same replacement ratio of natural aggregates by recycled aggregates obtained from concrete paving blocks. Fig. 27 shows the compressive strengths at 28 days for the reference mixes without the recycled aggregate. In our research, mix with designation C-0 was designed and is highlighted by a bold border of

Fig. 27. Comparison of compressive strength versus w/c ratio at 28 days of reference concrete mixtures.

the bar graph. It can be seen that the compressive strength of the C-0 mix (69.6 MPa) is the highest from this data set with w/c ratio of 0.42.

In the Fig. 28, the values of compressive strength at 28 days versus w/c ratio are shown for mixtures with a replacement of natural fine aggregate by recycled fine aggregate obtained from concrete paving blocks in the amount of 50%. Unfortunately, there was only one study [28] with the same replacement ratio of fine aggregate. Result of mixture designed in this study (C-50f) is again highlighted by a bold border of the bar graph and it can be seen that with w/c ratio of 0.42 the compressive strength is about 20% higher. However, it needs to be mentioned, that in the research by Bravo-German et al. [28] used old concrete paving blocks were utilised, which might affect the quality of

Fig. 28. Comparison of compressive strength versus w/c ratio at 28 days of concretes with 50% of natural fine aggregate replaced by recycled fine aggregate obtained from concrete paving blocks.

Table 6

Comparison of the results of concrete compressive strengths at 28 days from similar studies.

Research	$f_{c,CPB}$ (MPa)	Designation	Substitution of NFA (%)	Substitution % of NCA (%)	w/c	$f_{c,28}$ (MPa)
Pizon et al. (current research)	43.7	C-0 (reference)	0	0	0.42	69.6
		C-50f	50	0		65.9
		C-50c	0	50		64.8
		C-50fc	50	50		62.3
Wadhah et al. [26]	n.a.	CPA-0% (reference)	0	0	0.55	50.0
		CPA-50%	0	50		44.0
		CPA-100%	0	100		53.0
Zhang et al. [27]	n.a.	RA0 (reference)	0	0	0.33	54.0
		RA50	50	50		50.0
Bravo-German et al. [28]	n.a.	M1	0	0	0.36	60.9
		M2	50	0		54.8
		M4	0	50		56.1
		M5	50	50		42.6
		REF (reference)	0	0		46.1
Kočí et al. [29]	66.8	REC50	0	50	0.45	56.8
		REC100	0	100		54.5

this sorted waste material.

The compressive strengths at 28 days in the case of 50 % replacement of coarse natural aggregate by recycled coarse aggregate from concrete paving blocks are shown in Fig. 29. Result of mixture designed in this study (C-50c) is again highlighted by a bold border of the bar graph and it can be seen that with w/c ratio of 0.42 the compressive strength is the highest from this dataset. The mixture M4 from research by Bravo-German et al. [28] with lower w/c ratio of 0.36 shows about 13 % lower values of compressive strength. Higher w/c ratio also led to lower values of compressive strength.

Finally, the last graph, see Fig. 30, is dedicated to the comparison of compressive strength at 28 days in the case of replacement of 50 % of fine and 50 % of coarse natural aggregate by 50 % of recycled fine and 50 % of recycled coarse aggregated obtained from concrete paving blocks. Result of mixture designed in this study (C-50fc) is again highlighted by a bold border of the bar graph and it can be seen that with w/c ratio of 0.42 the compressive strength is again the highest in this dataset. Even with lower w/c ratio the result of compressive strength is about 20 % (mixture RA50) and 30 % (mixture M5) lower.

The former issue is connected with internal curing and the effective water-cement ratio. The high porosity of the recycled aggregate contributes to its effectiveness as an internal curing agent. The porous structure allows for the absorption and retention of water, which can be released during the curing process, thereby reducing the risk of cracking due to shrinkage and enhancing compressive strength [64]. This characteristic is particularly advantageous in environments where external curing methods may be less effective or feasible. The moisture supplied by the recycled aggregates can help maintain a favourable environment for hydration, leading to a denser microstructure and improved mechanical properties [65,66]. Furthermore, the relationship between the w/c ratio and the compressive strength of recycled aggregate concrete (RC) has been extensively studied. Kong et al. [67] established a generalised form of Abrams' Law for concrete made with both natural and recycled aggregates, demonstrating a strong correlation between the effective w/c ratio and compressive strength. Their findings suggest that as the w/c ratio increases, the compressive strength of RC tends to decrease, highlighting the importance of optimising the w/c ratio to achieve desired strength characteristics. The issue is also related to the amount of adhered old cement paste to aggregate in RCA, higher porosity of concrete and the weaker interfacial transition zone (ITZ). Studies have shown that the amount of adhered mortar on RCA plays a crucial role in determining the mechanical properties of the new concrete or mortar produced. Higher amounts of adhered mortar can lead to lower compressive strength and increased porosity, which in turn affects the overall durability and performance of the mortar [68–70]. For instance, the work of Zhao et al. [71] highlights that fine RCA can lead to a decrease in the mechanical strength of mortars due to the inherent characteristics of recycled materials [71]. The ITZ between the RCA and

Comparison of compressive strength vs. w/c ratio at 28 days

Fig. 30. Comparison of compressive strength versus w/c ratio at 28 days of concretes with 50 % of natural fine and 50 % of natural coarse aggregate replaced by recycled fine and coarse aggregate obtained from concrete paving blocks.

the new cement matrix is typically weaker and more porous than that found in conventional concrete, which can lead to inconsistencies in strength and durability [56]. The problem of lowered mechanical properties may be also mitigated using the pre-soaking process. Research indicates that pre-wetting RCA can lead to significant improvements in the compressive strength of RC. Strength of RC could increase by up to 9.4 % at 60 days when pre-wetted RCA was utilised, with the effects becoming more pronounced after 28 days of curing. This is attributed to the ability of the pre-wetted aggregates to release moisture gradually, thus sustaining hydration in the cement paste over an extended period [72]. Also various mixing and threating procedures may enhance the ITZ [3].

The microstructural differences between the concrete made with NA and RCA are significant and influence various performance characteristics of the concrete. One of the most notable differences is the porosity and density of the aggregates. RCA typically has higher porosity compared to NA, which leads to increased water absorption and lower density. This porosity is largely due to the adhered cement paste of the original concrete [73]. The ITZ in RCA concrete is often characterised by a higher degree of microcracking and a looser structure compared to that in concrete made with NA. The presence of these microcracks can significantly affect the mechanical properties of the concrete, including its compressive strength and durability [74,75]. The use of supplementary materials, such as silica fume or nano-silica, can alter the microstructure of both NA and RCA concrete. These materials can fill voids and enhance the densification of the ITZ, improving the overall mechanical properties of concrete [76,77].

8. Conclusions and further research directions

The results for mortars and concretes are consistent. Mortars require more superplasticizer (0.93–3.67 % m.c. for mortars, and 0.03 % m.c. for concrete) to achieve proper workability, which is related to the cement amount per volume of composite and the fineness of recycled aggregate. There is not only a change in flowability visible, but also the viscosity of mixtures varies if recycled aggregate is used. It indicates a different potential behaviour in pumpability and the ability to compact the mixture in the formwork.

Addition of recycled CPB aggregate decreased yield stress and increased plastic viscosity (by 47 % and 42 %, respectively, for measurement after 5 min from mixing, and 49 % and 61 %, respectively, for measurement after 60 min from mixing) even though flow diameter was comparable. Significant increase in yield stress was observed during 60 min, as for both reference mortar and mortar with 25 % recycled aggregate addition the increase was 71 % and 60 %, respectively, while plastic viscosity decreased to significantly lower extend (17 % and 9 % respectively).

Comparison of compressive strength vs. w/c ratio at 28 days

Fig. 29. Comparison of compressive strength versus w/c ratio at 28 days of concretes with 50 % of natural coarse aggregate replaced by recycled coarse aggregate obtained from concrete paving blocks.

Density of mortars in plastic and hardened state drops with raising recycled CPB aggregate content. The maximum decrease recorded for the 100 % replacement level is of 8 % for fresh mortars and about 10 % for hardened mortars. Density of hardened concrete is smaller by 5 % for 50 % of both aggregates' replacement. For replacement of one or another aggregate the decrease is of 3 %. It is connected strictly to lower density of recycled aggregate.

The porosity and absorbability increase proportionally to recycled aggregate content. For mortars the increase of porosity is 7 percentage points (pt.), while increase of absorbability is only 3.6 pt. comparing 0 % and 100 % replacement of aggregate. Increase of concretes porosity is 2.5 pt. – 3.0 pt. and increase of absorbability between 1 pt. and 2 pt. depending on the fraction and amount of aggregate replaced. It is connected strictly to higher porosity and absorbability of recycled aggregate.

The compressive strength of mortars exhibits two different patterns. The first one is true for the early strength. The compressive strength is reaching its optimum at 50 % of recycled aggregate content, and it is higher by 12 % and 19 % compared to reference one after 3 and 7 days respectively. This improvement is caused by a decrease in the effective w/c ratio. The second pattern is true for late compressive strength. Compressive strength is similar for mortars with 0–75 % of recycled aggregate. 100 % replacement level leads to significant decrease of 13 % and 20 % after 28 and 112 days respectively. In the case of concretes, the early compressive strength of concretes with recycled aggregate was similar or even greater as of the reference concrete, depending on the replacement level and the grading of the substituted aggregate. After 28 days and later, all concretes with recycled aggregates exhibited decreasing strength compared to the reference mixture. However, it needs to be noted, that in comparison to other studies focused on utilising CPB as aggregate replacement, our mixtures show the highest values of compressive strength at 28 days of testing.

The study monitored also the bulk electrical resistivity of concrete mixtures over 224 days to assess the aging and durability. Initial measurements at 7 days showed that all the measured values on concrete made of RCA were close to the value of reference concrete, indicating comparable early hydration progress. As the concrete matured, the differences in resistivity narrowed further. At the final measurement point (224 days), the resistivity of C-50f (9.47 kΩcm) and C-50c (9.50 kΩcm) converged with the reference (9.50 kΩcm), while C-50fc (8.98 kΩcm) remained slightly lower. These results demonstrate that all concrete mixtures exhibited consistent resistivity trends over time, with minor deviations (2.7 % on average) that did not significantly affect overall performance compared to the reference concrete. All concrete mixtures can be classified as having moderate resistance to chloride penetration according to ASTM C1876 [44].

Based on the results, it seems to be beneficial to use recycled paving blocks as a selected waste material to substitute natural aggregate in mortar and concrete mixtures. The issues concerning consistency drop may be mitigated using water reducing agents, and the proper treatment of the aggregate prior to its application could lead to a further improvement in consistency and also improve mechanical characteristics.

Future research should also focus on utilising crushed paving blocks sourced from actual pavement demolition projects as a substitution for natural aggregate in concrete. A critical aspect of this research should involve a detailed analysis of the potential impurities that may be present in the recycled material, such as oil, clay, or other contaminants. These impurities could significantly affect the concrete's mechanical properties, durability, and long-term performance. Investigating effective methods for impurity detection, removal or mitigation would enhance the feasibility and reliability of using recycled paving blocks in structural concrete applications. The studies could explore the influence of different levels and types of contamination on the properties of the resulting concrete to establish guidelines for material preparation and usage.

The data used in this research are published in the repository [78].

CRediT authorship contribution statement

Pizoń Jan: Writing – review & editing, Writing – original draft, Resources, Methodology, Investigation, Funding acquisition, Formal analysis, Data curation, Conceptualization. **Hornáková Marie:** Writing – review & editing, Writing – original draft, Visualization, Project administration, Funding acquisition, Formal analysis. **Matýšková Kateřina:** Writing – original draft, Methodology, Funding acquisition, Formal analysis. **Gołaszewska Małgorzata:** Supervision, Methodology, Formal analysis, Data curation. **Kratošová Gabriela:** Investigation, Conceptualization.

Declaration of Competing Interest

The authors declare that they have no known competing financial interests or personal relationships that could have appeared to influence the work reported in this paper.

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Data availability

The data presented in this study are available on Zenodo <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.15221865>

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